

Murad Reis Mosque in Rhodes

also known as “Murat Reis Camii”

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Entry tags: Greece, Rhodes, Religious Group, Abrahamic, Greek, Aegean, Cemetery, Islam, Sufism, Bektashi, Religious Place, Dodecanese, Language, Turkic, Islamic Traditions, Sunni, Hanafi

The mosque of Murad Reis is located outside of the walls of the Old City of Rhodes, on a cape to the north of Mandraki Port. In addition to the mosque, the mosque complex includes a dervish lodge of the Bektashi order, fountains, a rose garden, and a cemetery that includes the tomb of Murad Reis. The dervish tekke consisted of two buildings, one of which had living quarters for the sheikh and his family. In his travelogue from ca. 1671, Evliya Celebi mentions a grave in the cemetery dated to 965 AH (1557-1558 CE); and dates the inscription on the Bektashi lodge to 1018 AH (1609/1610 CE), which is also the date of Murad Reis' death. The mosque was constructed by Ebubekir Pasha ca. 1622, a century after the Ottoman conquest of Rhodes; the marble plaque above the entrance to the mosque carries the date of repairs made in 1797 CE. The mosque is built on a square plan, surmounted by an octagonal drum bearing a single dome, and is oriented toward the qibla. The minaret of the mosque was heavily remodeled during the Italian occupation of the island from 1912 to 1947; it originally had a conical spire, which is now spherical. During the period of Italian rule, the cemetery and rose garden were condensed to a smaller area than their original extent, meaning that many of the tombstones are no longer in their original positions; additionally, no new tombstones or burials were added after 1912. The final sheikh to reside at the tekke was Sheikh Suleiman Kaşlıoğlu, who was the last Mufti of Rhodes and who died in 1974. The Muslim community of Rhodes continued celebrating weddings, Mawlid, and circumcisions at the complex until 2018, at which time the tekke was converted into a music school by the Council of Monuments. Within the complex, the mosque is no longer in use or open to the public.

Date Range: 1557 CE - 2018 CE

Region: Murad Reis Mosque in Rhodes

Region tags: Greece

Murad Reis Mosque in Rhodes is located to the north of the Old Town.

Status of Participants:

✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

— Source 1: Barnes, John Robert. “List of Books and Journals Formerly in the Possession of Şeyh Süleyman Kaşlıoğlu, Şeyh of the Murad Reis Tekye and the Last Müfti of Rhodes (1884-1974).” Archives of the Dodecanese, 2007.

- Source 1: Evliya. Evliya Çelebi Seyahatnamesi. Translated by Seyit Ali Kahraman. Vol. 9/1. Yapı Kredi Yayınları, 2010.
- Source 2: Evliya. Evliya Çelebi, Evliya Çelebi Seyahatnamesi, Vol. IX. Translated by Yücel Dağlı, Seyit Ali Kahraman, and Robert Dankoff, 2005.
- Source 1: Konuk, Neval. Midilli, Rodos, Sakız, ve İstanköy'de Osmanlı Mimarisi/Ottoman Architecture in Lesvos, Rhodes, Chios and Kos Islands. Ankara, 2008.
Notes: pp. 52-53, 84-85, 90-91, 98-105, 106-107, 114-119, 202, 208-209, 230.
- Source 1: Economides, Regina. "Murat Reis Complex, in Ottoman Architecture in Greece, Pp. 378-379." edited by Ersi Brouskari. Hellenic Ministry of Culture, 2008.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <http://tourism.rhodes.gr/?p=9258&lang=en>
- Source 1 Description: This is the online source of the Municipality of Rhodes. However, it should be noted that Murat Reis was born in Rhodes, and died in a naval battle near Cyprus.
- Source 1 URL: <https://www.aa.com.tr/en/europe/greece-turns-spiritual-center-of-muslim-turks-on-rhodes-island-into-music-faculty/2719657>
- Source 1 Description: Article describing the end of religious celebrations at the tekke following its conversion to a music school in 2018.

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– No

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

- Other [specify]: This mosque was originally associated with a rose garden.

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

Type of feature

- Plantings
- Other [specify]: Garden

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

Notes: The mosque complex is located outside of the city walls of Rhodes, near Kadirga port (today, Mandraki Port).

↳ Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– Yes

↳ Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

– No

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

Notes: Türbe of Murad Reis

↳ A single structure

– Yes

Notes: Türbe of Murad Reis

↳ The structure has a definite shape

–Other [specify]: Octagonal

↳ One single feature

–Other [specify]: N/A.

↳ A group of structures:

– No

↳ A group of features:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Yes

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Memorial

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

Notes: The türbe of Murad Reis was modified through the offerings (prayer rugs, lamps, hides) that visitors left.

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– No

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

– Yes

Notes: Cemetery of ca. 1557 - 1912

↳ A single structure

– No

↳ One single feature

–Other [specify]: N/A.

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

↳ A group of features:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Yes

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Memorial

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– Yes

Notes: During Italian rule of Rhodes (1912-1947), the cemetery was significantly decreased in size, meaning that the tombstones were rearranged within a smaller area. In addition, many of the türbes have been vandalized.

↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed

–Other [specify]: Size reduction

↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:

–For political reasons

↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:

–Other [specify]: N/A.

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

– Yes

Notes: Rose garden

↳ A single structure

– No

↳ One single feature

– Purposefully placed plants

↳ A group of structures:

– No

↳ A group of features:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Yes

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

–Other [specify]: Beauty and contemplation

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– Yes

↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed

–Other [specify]: Necessary upkeep

↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:

–For political reasons

Notes: The garden experienced major rearrangement under Italian rule between 1912 and 1947. Additionally, the last volunteer caretaker Saban Karginlioglu died in 2018; the Council of Monuments now controls the complex.

↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:

–Natural phenomena

– Yes

Notes: Dervish tekke

↳ A single structure

– No

↳ One single feature

–Other [specify]: N/A.

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

↳ A group of features:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Yes

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Social

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– No

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

– Yes

Notes: Murad Reis Mosque

↳ A single structure

– Yes

Notes: Murad Reis Mosque

↳ The structure has a definite shape

– Square

↳ One single feature

– Other [specify]: N/A.

↳ A group of structures:

– No

Notes: Cemetery

↳ A group of features:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Yes

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Individual

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Communal

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– No

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

↳ Specify

– Other [specify]: Government official

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

↳ Groups:

– Specialized labourers/craftspeople

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Notes: While the site of the mosque was likely not Murad Reis' exact birthplace, he was born on Rhodes.

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Yes

↳ Specify

– Other [specify]: Death of namesake

Notes: The mosque was built shortly after the death of naval commander Murad Reis.

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Yes

↳ Is this sponsor of the same religious group/tradition as the main usage of the place:

– Yes

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expression of devotion with no expectation of favor in return

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– No

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Yes

Notes: Originally, the structures were arranged around the rose garden; the dervish lodge was also a central feature of the area.

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth
– No

↳ Sand
– No

↳ Clay
– No

↳ Plaster
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Wood
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Grass
– No

↳ Stone
– Yes

|

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: N/A.

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

–Yes [specify]: Paint

Notes: The interior of the mosque is plastered and painted. The interior of the dome is painted blue with gold stars; the interior walls are painted yellow with designs in red and green. The most recent phase of interior decoration is from the twentieth century.

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– Yes

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

Notes: There are movable tapestries with verses from the Quran inside the mosque.

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

↳ Floral motifs

– Yes

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: N/A.

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– Yes

↳ Reliefs representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– No

↳ Reliefs representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Reliefs representing human/historical narratives:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Inscription

Notes: The dedicatory plaque above the entrance to the mosque is carved in relief.

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Yes

↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:

– No

↳ Are they wall paintings:

– Yes

↳ Type

–Other [specify]: Geometric paintings on interior moldings.

↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:

– No

↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: N/A.

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– Yes

Notes: In the courtyard between the mosque and the cemetery, there is a traditional Rhodian black-and-white pebble mosaic. Pebble mosaics of this type occur throughout the Old City of Rhodes, in both domestic and religious contexts, with the earliest examples at the Rhodes Archaeological Museum dating from the Roman period.

↳ Mosaics representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– No

↳ Mosaics representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Mosaics representing human/historical narratives:

– No

↳ Abstract mosaics:

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: N/A.

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

Notes: The inscription above the doorway to the mosque notes that it was renovated in 1797-1798.

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative
[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– Yes

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: N/A.

↳ Other type of decoration:

– No

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– No

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– Yes

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

Notes: Visiting ca. 1671, Evliya Celebi wrote that offerings came to the mausoleum of Murad Reis from all over. The stone sarcophagus was covered with green cloth, and surrounded by lamps, banners, hides, and prayer rugs.

Reference: Evliya. *Evliya çelebi seyahatnamesi*. Translated by Seyit Ali Kahraman. Vol. 9/1. Yapı Kredi Yayınları, 2010pp. 257-274. p.277

↳ Personal effects:

– No

↳ Valuable/precious items:

– Yes

↳ Significant value:

Gold, jade, intensely worked objects, or meaningful symbolic value

– No

↳ Some value, valuable or useful objects:

– Yes

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Lamps, banners, hides, and prayer rugs as offerings outside the burial

↳ Other

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

↳ Family tomb/crypt:

– No

↳ Domestic context:

Interred beneath floors of house, or in areas of domestic activity

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Several türbes (mausoleums) of individuals.

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: While a monotheistic deity was worshipped at this site, the deity was not considered to be physically manifested there ("present.")

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:

– No

↳ Are they sky deity:

– No

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)

– No

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

– No

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:

– No

↳ Are they unquestionably good:

– Yes

↳ Are they other:

– Other [specify]: N/A.

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination practices:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Sir Arthur Evans reported divination practices from Bektashis in Albania ca. 1901; it is possible that Bektashis in Rhodes practiced divination as well, but this subject would require

further research.

Reference: Evans, Arthur. "Mycenaean Tree and Pillar Cult and Its Mediterranean Relations", 1901.

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: N/A.

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be seen:

– Yes

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be physically felt:

– Yes

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

Do visitors communicate with gods:

– Yes

Notes: Visitors communicated with the monotheistic deity through prayer.

Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: Some visitors may have communicated with angels and/or djinn.

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

–specify: 50-100

How often do these rituals take place:

–specify: Daily

Notes: Daily prayers occurred 5 times per day, potentially with additional morning and noon

prayers added in accordance with Bektashi practices.

– specify: Weekly

Notes: Friday prayer took place once per week.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– No

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– No

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– Yes

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– No

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

Notes: Evliya Celebi, writing in ca. 1671, described the lamps, hides, banners, and prayer rugs at the tomb of Murad Reis as offerings.

↳ Are material offerings mandatory:

– No

↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

– No

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: N/A.

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– No

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– No

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– No

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Irregular repairs

Notes: There were irregular repairs, such as those of 1797-1798.

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

Notes: Visitors made pilgrimage to the türbe of Murad Reis.

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

–optional (rare)

↳ Are pilgrimages the main reason for construction/establishment of the place:

– No

↳ Are pilgrimages to this place associated with significant life events:

– No

↳ Does pilgrimage to this place involve following established routes (roads):

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Are festivals present:

– Yes

Notes: Prior to 2018, the Muslim community of Rhodes celebrated weddings, mawlid, and circumcisions at the complex. The tekke has since been confiscated by the Council of Monuments and converted into a music school.

↳ Frequency of festivals

– specify: Weekly/Monthly

↳ Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s):

– All members

↳ Are festivals a defining element in the construction/decoration of the place:

– No

↳ On average, how many participants gather at this place:

– number: 50-200

↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s):

– Yes

↳ Is food consumption limited to certain members of the population:

– Non-elites

Notes: Consumption was not limited to certain members.

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– Field doesn't know

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

↳ Present full time

– No

↳ Present part time

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Yes

Notes: The sheikh who lived at the mosque complex was a man.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– No

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Yes

Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:

– No

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Yes

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Yes

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Yes

Is a bureaucracy present permanently:

– No

Is a bureaucracy present on a temporary or seasonal basis:

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Yes

Is this control the primary supporting income of this place:

– Yes

Does this place lease out land:

– Yes

↳ Does this place lease out tools:

– No

– Yes

↳ Is this control the primary supporting income of this place:

– Yes

↳ Does this place lease out land:

– Yes

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Yes

↳ Public food distribution and/or storage:

– Yes

Notes: Evliya Celebi describes the high quality of grape cultivation associated with the tekke.

Reference: Evliya. Evliya çelebi seyahatnamesi. Translated by Seyit Ali Kahraman. Vol. 9/1. Yapı Kredi Yayınları, 2010pp. 257-274. p.277

↳ Place for civic functions (census, elections, others):

– No

↳ Place for the practice of justice (trials, executions, etc.):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Function for water management:

– No

↳ Part of the transportation network:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: N/A.

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

↳ Are they written at this place:

– No

↳ Are they oral:

– Yes

Notes: In addition to existing in written form, the Quran was memorized and recited.

↳ Is there a story associated with the origin and/or construction of this place:

– No

↳ Are there religious specialists in charge of interpreting the scriptures:

– No

Notes: Religious specialists provided interpretation and guidance, but did not hold a monopoly over interpretation.

↳ Are the scriptures part of the building/place:

– Yes

↳ Attached to the structures as decoration:

– Yes

↳ Housed within the place/structure:

– Yes

↳ As dedicatory inscription(s):

– No

Other

–Other [specify]: N/A.

– Yes

Bibliography

General References

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Reference: Field doesn't know, Evans, Arthur. "Mycenaean Tree and Pillar Cult and Its Mediterranean Relations", 1901.